

ISic4422

Epitaph for Artemidoros (?)

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

plinth

Editor

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2016 visited museum

Last Change

2020-05-28 - Jonathan Prag created the file from template, publications, and photographs

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

From the area of the necropolis in contrada Cardusa , but without exact provenance

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Tripi, Museo Archeologico Santi Furnari di Tripi, inventory ME23440

Physical Description

Incomplete plinth of the local sandstone belonging to a tomb of the epitombion type C. A moulding is largely preserved around the base; the upper surface is cut roughly smooth, but does not appear to be the original surface, and the upper/right part of the text across the front face is lost (as is the right corner of the block).

Dimensions

Height 18.5 cm

Width 46 cm

Depth 49 cm

Layout

A single line of rather irregular Greek letters, seemingly not precisely centred on the stone, with empty space below; the right hand end of the text is lost to damage.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Somewhat crudely cut and rather irregular letters. Alpha has straight bar; rho has somewhat elongated closed eye; epsilon has shorter middle bar; mu has vertical first and last strokes, mid-strokes formed by diagonals which meet about half-way down; delta is rather small and off-vertical; omega appears to be small, above the line, open, and with outward and downward angled arms.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 29 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. Ἀρτεμιδω[ρου]

Apparatus

text from photograph
Sofia 2018: Ἀρτεμίδ[---]

Translation (en)

(tomb) of Artemidoros

Commentary

Traces of an omega are visible after the delta, which makes restoration of the extremely common name Ἀρτεμίδωρος [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?name=%E1%BC%88%CF%81%CF%84%CE%B5%CE%BC%CE%AF%CE%B4%CF%89%CF%81%CE%BF%CF%82] almost certain (the name is very common at nearby Tauromenion). The epitaph can be assumed to be in the genitive, after the pattern of the majority of epitaphs in this necropolis.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Sofia, G. 2015. Abakainon. Nella dimora di Ade. La necropoli in contrada Cardusa a Tripi. Terme Vigliatore (ME). At 116 fig.120

Sofia, G. 2018. Nuove iscrizioni funerarie dalla necropoli di Abakainon. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 206: 103-112. At 108 no.12 and fig.13

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